

OSCAR Knowledge Graph and Contextual, Graph-based Learning Path Recommendation Algorithm for the Personalized Learning Environment eDoer

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1. Introduction

In the scope of OSCAR project, the data model used for the educational content has been investigated and developed to provide more connectivity between open educational resources (OERs), which are created by different experts and/or in different periods of time. Data model development focused on transferring the tree structure of the database into a network structure, in the form of a knowledge graph.

While the first knowledge graph structure has been planned and implemented in the first year of the project, the knowledge graph has been further extended in the second year. The extension included enriching the text mining pipelines that are used to extract the relations between courses and topics. The extension also included handling the multilingualism of the data, allowing the connection between learning materials in English and German.

Based on the knowledge graph, the recommendation algorithm has been developed. The recommender system is designed to recommend learning paths for learners, based on the context in which the learning takes place. The learning path recommendation algorithm is designed as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) with a contextualized reward function. This allows the system to take into account the learner's current situation, learning goal, and background knowledge when making recommendations.

The contextual recommendations rely on an extended learner profile. The user profile extension has been made based on a literature review of the contextual factors used in technology enhanced learning (TEL). This enabled the user profile to include factors on the context of learner context, such as the learner's background knowledge, time availability, and goal orientation, which are then fed to the recommendation system.

In the following sections, the previous points will be further discussed and elaborated in detail. This report will provide an in-depth look at the development of the technical aspects of the project, including the data model, text mining pipelines, recommendation algorithm, and user profile extension. Additionally, the report will also present the evaluation framework of the system and discuss future work and applications.

2. OSCAR knowledge graph as a network data-model

Educational content that an expert created on the eDoer platform has a high likelihood to be similar to other educational content created by other experts. This is especially the case where experts from the same domain create different courses and topics in the system. OSCAR knowledge graph is a network data model that is developed to represent the similarities between courses, topics and their learning materials as relations that connect them in one graph structure. Fig.1 shows the transfer from tree data model to a network one, and the additional connectivity between the Journeys.

Fig.1. Knowledge graph as a network data model in comparison to tree data structures. The relations of the type “has_course” and “has_topic” are defined by experts, while relations of the type “has_semantic_relation_to” are mined through the semantic-similarity algorithms.

2.1. Graph-node types and attributes

OSCAR knowledge graph is based on the taxonomical levels that were developed for the eDoer platform. Node types in the graph database are then denied based on that taxonomy as follows:

1. Journey: which represents a learning goal that includes all the knowledge elements needed to accomplish it.
2. Course: a container that represents one aspect of the learning goal.
3. Topic: a concrete knowledge element, which represents a single concept. A group of Topics form a Course.
4. Educational Package: a group of related and ordered (preferably open) educational resources (OERs) for a single Topic.
5. Educational Content: a concrete OER that can be studied by the learner.

Table 1 describes node types in the dataset, their neo4j labels and the node attributes associated with them.

Table 1. Graph-node types and attributes

Node Type	Neo4j Label	Node attributes
Journey	Journey	ID: int Title: str Description: str Embedding_model: str Industry: str Language: str Company: str Country: str City: str Created_at: datetime Updated_at: datetime
Course	Course	ID: int Title: str Description: str Embedding_model: str Language: str Learnable: boolean Assessable: boolean Addable: boolean Created_at: datetime Updated_at: datetime
Topic	Topic	ID: int Title: str Description: str Embedding_model: str Language: str Learnable: boolean Assessable: boolean Created_at: datetime Updated_at: datetime
Educational Package	Educational_Package	ID: int Title: str Description: str Embedding_model: str Created_at: datetime Updated_at: datetime

Educational Content	OER	ID: int Title: str Description: str Embedding_model: str Url: str Created_at: datetime Updated_at: datetime
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2.2. Graph-relation types and attributes

Experts define the previous relations between the different taxonomical levels, while the relations between elements of the same level, as well as elements from elements that belong to multiple Journeys are extracted through automated semantic-similarity algorithms, see Fig.1. Both graph nodes, i.e. the elements corresponding to the taxonomical levels, and the graph relations, defined by experts and the algorithms, form then the overall knowledge graph in OSCAR.

Graph relations include the ones defined by the original taxonomy, and the new semantic relations extracted from the textual similarities. Table 2 describes relation types in the graph dataset and their attributes in neo4j.

Table2. Graph-node types and attributes

Relation type	Neo4j label	Relation attributes
Journey-Course relation	has_curse	ID: int
Course-Topic relation	has_topic	ID: int
Topic-Educational_Package relation	has_educational_package	ID: int
Educational_Package-Educational_Content relation	has_oer	ID: int
Course-Course Topic-Topic	has_semantic_relation_to	ID: int Title_similarity_score: float Description_similarity_score: float

The knowledge graph node and relation details have been explained in the technical report on OSCAR graph implementation roadmap¹.

¹ Knowledge Graph Implementation Roadmap for our Personalised Learning Environment:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5878852>

The development of OSCAR knowledge graph in the second phase of the project included enhancing the accuracy of relation extraction algorithms, through extending the text-mining pipelines used to mine the textual similarity between the elements on the graph. Moreover, semantic similarity extraction was also extended to include other languages than English, namely German language, to cover more of the content that is created by experts in German.

3. Relation extraction development through text mining

3.1. Data pre-processing:

Metadata that is associated with each taxonomical level is analysed before using it to create the graph model. The textual content of the metadata (titles and description fields) is pre-processed based on the following steps, to enhance the performance of text mining algorithms.

1. Language detection: Journeys in the data set are created in both German and English languages. A language detection step is conducted to enable language-dependent text mining.
2. Text cleaning: Where special characters, symbols and URLs are removed from the textual fields. Semantic structure of the sentences is kept intact in this step, since text similarities are to be calculated on a semantic level, not as a bag-of-words (BOW).
3. Text translation: to enable a comparison and textual similarity detection between German and English strings, Each German text is translated through DeepL API.
4. Text embedding: language-dependent models (SBERT and Spacy) are used to create the embeddings of the title and description texts.

3.2. Text mining pipeline:

A custom text mining pipeline is implemented to extract semantic relations among Courses, among Topics, and between Courses and Topics based on semantic textual similarities between the titles and descriptions of the Courses and Topics. The pipeline is designed to handle both titles (short textual content) and descriptions (long textual content) in both English and German languages, see Fig.2.

The text pre-processing steps are followed by two different processing and matching paths for titles and descriptions. The titles are processed by creating title embeddings that are accurate in both English and German using the Reimers and Gurevych model, namely Sentence-BERT and the Spacy library for natural language processing (NLP) in Python. The semantic textual similarities between the titles are calculated using the cosine similarity algorithm. Titles in different languages are embedded in different corpus spaces, and thus, the German title is translated to English before the cosine similarity is calculated, using the DeepL API translation service.

In contrast, an additional step is added for the processing of descriptions due to the higher volume of text. The descriptions may include multiple topics that are relevant to them, providing information about potential relevance to other Courses and Topic nodes in the database. Therefore, a topic extraction step is implemented in the pipeline to mine the main topics from its long content, analyzing the key phrases in the text using the KeyBERT model. Text embeddings are created for extracted topics similarly to titles. The comparison between descriptions is done by comparing the set of description-topics from

one node to the set of topics from the other. An intersection matrix is created to determine pairs of topics to be compared, and a cosine similarity score is calculated for each pair.

Once all topic-pair similarities are calculated, a rule-based algorithm calculates the final similarity average, across all topics of both nodes. The resulting score from titles and descriptions are then used to determine if a semantic relation between the two nodes in the graph is created, based on a 0.8 similarity threshold for titles and 0.65 for descriptions.

Fig.2 Text mining pipeline for semantic relation extraction

4. User profile extension for contextual recommendations

In order to enable contextualized recommendations for the learners using eDoer platform, OSCAR project developed a graph-based, context-aware recommender system, which enables suggesting learning paths for the learners, based on their learning context.

Contextualizing the learning path recommendations begins with the concrete definition of the learning context, and continues to define the factors that describe that contexts, in order to embed them in the learner profile, and thus enable the recommender systems of accounting for them while generating the recommendation.

Based on a literature analysis of the relevant papers in the domain of technology enhanced learning, context-aware educational recommendations and contextual factors in user profiles, within the last 10 years, a concrete definition of the learning context has been adopted from Buchmann, 2022 as follows:

Learning Context is defined as the situation, in which learning happens, which includes the learner's situation (location, previous knowledge, etc.) and the learning object's situation (type, length, implementation scenario, etc.).

Fig.3 shows an overview on the spectrum of context dimensions that have been researched and defined in the field of TEL. These dimensions correspond to the context definition and other earlier definitions of the learning context, such as in Abowd et al.² and Verbert et al.³ Table 3 describes a range of elements that describe those dimensions within the TEL domain.

Fig.3 Context dimensions in TEL

Based on the literature survey of the last 10 years, we mapped the context factors based on their relevance to the pedagogical and technical domains, in order to enhance the selection of the factors we used in the final recommendation system. Fig. 4 shows the resulting map, with the relevance of the factors to both domains. The size of the factor represents the frequency it was used in the surveyed literature.

² Towards a Better Understanding of Context and Context-Awareness. DOI: 10.1007/3-540-48157-5_29

³ Context-aware recommender systems for learning: a survey and future challenges. DOI: 10.1109/TLT.2012.11

Table 3. Elements of context dimensions in the TEL domain [Verbert et al.]

	Spatio-temporal		Physical conditions	Computing	Recourse		User	Activity	Social
	Location	Time			Virtual	physical			
Schilit et al.	User context		Physical context	Computing context			User context		User context
Chen and Kotz	User context	time	Physical context	Computing context			User context		User context
Schmidt et al.	Location	time	Physical conditions	infrastructure			User	Task	Social environment
Zimmermann et al.	Location	time		Artificial entity		Natural entity	Human entity	Activity	relations
Berri et al.				Technical			Learner		
Beale and Lonsdale	Environment						User	Tasks	Other users
Wang et al.	Location	Time		Facility			Identity	Activity	Community
Derntl and Hummel	World context			Device context	Digital context	Physical context	Learner information context		Physical context
Li et al.	Where	When			What		Who	How	
Schmidt				Technical			Personal	Organisationl	Social
Tankeleviciene and Damasevicius	Environment						Learner	Activities	Environment
Kurti	Location/environment						Person	Activity/task	Interpersonal
Hu and Moor	Spatio-temporal context						Personal	Task	role

Fig.4 Context factors map between pedagogical and technical fields [Abu-Rasheed et al.⁴]

⁴ Context based learning: a survey of contextual indicators for personalized and adaptive learning recommendations – a pedagogical and technical perspective. DOI: [10.3389/educ.2023.1210968](https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1210968)

5. Contextual, graph-based recommender system

Utilizing the contextual factors in the user profile and the information embedded in OSCAR knowledge graph about the educational content and its inter-relations, the recommendation algorithm is then developed to offer the learner with a context-aware, personalized learning-path toward their learning goal.

The learning path generated by the recommender system in OSCAR is composed of educational content from one or more learning journeys on the platform. This is possible due to the semantic connectivity of learning goals in the knowledge graph. For example, if a learner wishes to learn how to develop their career, they will choose that learning goal “career development” from the existing learning journeys in eDeor. Based on the learner’s profile, the recommender system generates a suggestion of a learning path, which may not only include topics about “project management” and “time management” for career development, but also topics about “stress management” and “finding balance between work and life” even though the last two topics are a part of another journey on “mental health for researchers”. The inclusion of those topics in a learning path that targets “career development” is a direct result of the semantic relations that have been discovered between the two learning goals, even though the two journeys were created by different experts. The learning path is then enriched with semantically relevant content from the knowledge graph. The choice of the additional content is based on the learner’s profile, which reflects the learning context of that particular learner. Therefore, the recommender system in OSCAR project is enveloped as a contextual, graph-based learning-path recommendation system.

The recommendation algorithm itself is developed using AI-based methods. We utilize the algorithm of reinforcement learning to search for the most suitable learning paths for the learner. Reinforcement learning is a type of machine learning that is used to teach agents (e.g. robots, software programs) how to make decisions. The agent is placed in an environment and learns to interact with that environment by taking actions at each environment-state, and then receiving rewards or penalties. The goal of the agent is to learn the best actions to take in order to maximize the rewards over time. It is a process based on the idea of trial and error. The agent starts with a set of actions it can take in the environment, and as it moves from one state to another, it takes an action and receives a reward or a penalty based on the results of its transition to the new state through that action, see Fig.5. Over time, the agent learns which actions are likely to lead to higher rewards and which actions should be avoided. As the agent learns, it can improve its decision-making and become more efficient at completing tasks or achieving goals.

In our recommendation algorithm, we define an agent in the form of a virtual learner. This virtual learner explores all the possible states and actions in the knowledge graph. We define a state as a node in the knowledge graph, which translates to being in the process of learning a course or a topic at the moment. The actions are defined as all the potential transitions from the current state of learning (current course or topic) to any other course or topic that are reachable in the graph. Reachability is then a result of being connected to the current state through a graph relation.

We developed a customized reward function, which assigns rewards and penalties for the virtual learner based on the profile of the real learner. The main concept is that the virtual agent will be rewarded as

long as it takes an action that results in generating a better learning path, contextually. Actions that lead to reaching a content that is not relevant to the learner’s context, will lead to a penalty.

Using sufficient computational power and an optimized graph exploration process, the recommender system algorithm is capable of exploring all the possible learning states and actions in the knowledge graph. The recommendation system then calculates the overall scores for each potential learning path and recommends the most suitable path to the real learner.

Fig.5. Reinforcement learning algorithm and its simplified environment in OSCAR data structure.

In Fig.5, a simple illustration of the recommendation logic is shown. Based on the learner’s context, a learning path is recommended. For example, learning path from S_0 to the learning goal through action A_1 (in green color) is recommended when the learner’s context is focused on reaching the final learning goal directly and in the shortest possible way. On the other hand, the learning path through states S_2 and S_3 (in orange) is recommended to learners whose context shows more time and exploration-preference of other relevant content in the knowledge graph.

From a long list of contextual factors, the ones that were most relevant to the OSCAR project are:

1. **Background knowledge of the learner:** which includes all the previously known topics and skills to the learner. This starting point allows the recommender system of connecting the learner to existing topics and courses in the knowledge graph. Once the first connection is found, the reinforcement learning algorithms continues to explore all potential graph paths between that learner and their learning goal.
2. **Goal orientation:** which is a factor that represents the learner’s preference to explore more relevant content in the knowledge graph. Relevant content is similar to the “stress management”

course in the example above, where it belongs to another learning goal, but still semantically relevant for the “career development” goal in some contexts.

3. **Time available for learning:** which is an essential factor that controls the length of the learning path, and the elements selected within it. This is a limiting factor that the recommender system considers, to prevent recommending paths that are not achievable by the learner based on their available time for learning.

In addition to those factors, other learner-profile data is also integrated in the reward function of the reinforcement learning algorithm, to account for the full learning situation of the learner at any stage of the learning process. Other user information includes, among others, their preferences for the type of content they wish to learn (e.g. videos, scripts, etc.).

While those factors are chosen in the scope of OSCAR project, it is important to mention that the reinforcement learning algorithm can integrate other factors as needed, by adjusting the reward function to include new ones.

The recommendation algorithm is also designed in the light of the expert’s input in the knowledge graph, which is represented by the structure of each learning goal (i.e. the courses and topics in the journey). The quality of the recommendation is supported by the quality of that content. Therefore, to account for the content and order of learning materials that an expert defined, the recommender system assigns additional weights to the expert-created learning-paths. Those weights influence the calculation of the rewards and penalties during the search for the most suitable learning path. The resulting recommendation is then not only based on the individual content of each course and topic, but also on the expert’s decision to order that content in a certain way.

6. Knowledge Graph API

Based on the software development plan for OSCAR project, which includes two recommendation systems working collaboratively in the eDeor platform, see Fig.6, the graph-based recommendation system is included in an overall structure of micro services, that are offered to the eDeor platform through an application programming interface (API).

Fig.6. Structure of the IT solution concept for integrating graph services into the eDoer learning platform.

Graph services include a range of features, see Table 2, that allows the system of:

1. Searching the graph for directly connected courses and topics
2. Expanding the graph search to multi-hop search for semantically connected content.
3. Getting graph analytical metrics for the nodes. Those include:
 - a. Node betweenness score
 - b. Node closeness score
 - c. Node community
4. Generating the recommended learning path for a user profile.

Table2. The endpoints in OSCAR’s knowledge graph API.

Endpoint	Description	Argument	Value	Return
get-course-from-n-hops	Get directly connected courses (hop=1) Get connected courses through one transitive hop (hop=2)	n_hop course_id	1, 2 [int]	Json format Property: courses, Value: list of course IDs
get-course-community	Get the course’s graph community	course_id	[int]	Json format

	(surrounding, interconnected course)			Property: courses, Value: list of course IDs
get-course-centrality-measure	Get Betweenness Centrality (the role a course plays in connecting other courses) or Closeness Centrality (the role a course plays as a centre of a group of courses, e.g. cluster centre)	measure course_id	betweenness, closeness [int]	Json format Property: course_betweenness OR course_closeness Value: normalised measure value, float
get-recommended-journey	Get the learning path recommendation.	userl_id User_bk user_lg user_t_w user_t_h user_go	[int] List[int] [int] [int] [int] True/False	Json format

7. Evaluation framework

The development of the knowledge graph data model and the recommendation system based on it has been equipped with an evaluation plan for each of the algorithms that were used to construct the knowledge graph and to recommend the learning path.

Evaluation of the knowledge graph construction and graph-based recommendation included quantitative and qualitative measures, which were implemented alongside the development of the construction pipelines, do assure that their performance meets the quality required in the eDeor platform.

7.1. Quantitative evaluation measures

Qualitative measures were selected to evaluate the performance of the text mining pipelines explained in (3.2), as well as the final knowledge graph structure. Text mining performance has been evaluated by comparing the textual similarity of graph nodes that were automatically connected, with those nodes that human content creators have connected. A sample of 240 semantic relations was randomly selected

from the total number of automatically created semantic relations. Then the similarity of the educational content (courses and topics) on each side of the relation was calculated. The latter similarity represented how a human expert would connect educational contents together while describing them textually. Results of the evaluation, see Fig.7, showed that the semantic relation extraction algorithm performance was comparable to the one of content curators, as long as the textual content provided is sufficient. This meant that the limitation of the relation extraction pipeline was that the sparsity of the textual content of courses or topics has disrupted the algorithm’s performance greatly.

Fig.7. Evaluation results of the KG semantic relation extraction

The evaluation of the knowledge graph itself was conducted through a set of graph metrics, which were interpreted in the domain of technology enhanced learning. Those metrics and their TEL-oriented interpretations are shown in Table 3.

Table3. Quantitative metrics for knowledge graph data model evaluation

Evaluation metric	Interpretation in learning	Preferred value trend
Average Degree Centrality	LO's connectedness to other objects that take place in the learning scenario	increasing
Clustering Coefficient (Number of communities)	Reflects the number of contexts that the KG represents	increasing
Clustering Coefficient (Average modularity score)	Reflects the potential to separate those learning contexts from each other	decreasing
Weakly Connected Components	Reflects poor connectedness of LO groups in the data model	decreasing
Betweenness Centrality	Nodes with high BC work as bridges, which link different parts of the graph together, allowing the learner to combined information from each Journey to solve a more complex problem	increasing

7.2. Qualitative evaluation

Qualitative feedback has been collected in a set of focus groups, which were planned alongside the knowledge graph construction in OSCAR project. The focus groups included mainly experts who were involved in the content creation process in eDeor platform. The feedback was collected based on a group of questions that were discussed to survey the opinion of an experienced content creator on the benefits they may achieve from the knowledge graph, as well as the construction methods used to create it. Three groups of experts have been invited to participate in the focus group discussions. Some of those focus groups took place on several sessions, to explore the knowledge graph construction more thoroughly, and enhance the methods that are followed to construct it. Focus groups are reported separately in another technical report in OSCAR project.

7.3. Experimental setup of the final evaluation

The evaluation and piloting phases in OSCAR project is conducted in the last year of the project. In the second project phase, a concrete plan has been developed to evaluate the graph-based recommendation algorithm. The plan was constructed with experts in learning analytics and organizational psychology, to ensure a statistically valid evaluation framework for the final testing rounds in OSCAR.

The evaluation of the graph-based recommender system is planned as an A/B test, as shown in Fig.8. Learners are randomly assigned to the treatment and control groups, where they will receive contextualized and static recommendations respectively. The goal of the test is to evaluate the learner's ability to solve a complex task, based on the recommended learning path.

The results of the evaluation is measured through the performance of the learner in the test, where test scores are the indicator. The survey before the experiment is meant to collect background information about the test candidate, to complete their profiles, and thus generate the contextual recommendation.

Fig.8. Evaluation plan for OSCAR’s contextual learning-path recommendation.

The design of the test includes preparing the educational materials used in the test, in terms of their quantity and the time they need. Additionally, the questions of the test are prepared and monitored to ensure their objectivity towards all test participants.

Participants of the test were workers in the health domain. There were presented with a real-world problem from their own context. Once the user profiles are created for the participants, they received a recommendation on learning material to study, in order to solve that problem within their own context. The ability of each participant to solve the complex problem was measured before and after the test in both experiment groups. The results showed that the participants in the treatment group expressed a better understanding of the complexity of the problem in hand, and therefore were able to provide a deeper solution approach for that problem. These results show the role of connecting education content in a graph structure, as well as the ability of the context-aware recommendation algorithm in corresponding to a learner’s context and provide a learning path that supports them in solving a complex, real-world problem.